

**A SURVEY OF ATTITUDE OF SELECTED MEDICAL
COLLEGE STUDENTS OF INDORE TOWARDS
GAMES AND SPORTS**

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INTRODUCTION

Games and sports have been of tremendous interest of people throughout the world. In our own country various types of games provided opportunities to the sports persons to display their talent and skill and for common man it was a source of entertainment. In order to acquire skill, various exercises and strategies were involved but no systematic and scientific methods were developed to improve the aspects mentioned above. It was visualized that if mental and physical training has to be imported it should start from early stage of life. Thus it emerged that sport activity should be combined with education. Our point of view is indicated when we come across old Persian literature of games and sports where it was claimed that young boys were trained in such activities as running, jumping, riding, javelin throwing etc. Similarly Egyptians, Babylonians and Jewish community patronized extensive Physical Education Programmes. The objective of education calls for the wholesome personality development of a child which includes development of physical and mental faculties in addition to social and emotional uplift of the child. Since human being is a combined of body, mind and spirit, he cannot be compartmentalized into body and mind separately. Therefore combining the world physical with education brings out a clear sense that the discipline, mental, social, emotional and spiritual development. It becomes interpretative that the newly born discipline of physical education should be put in to proper perspective and thoroughly studied for the welfare of humanity at large. In establishing the position of physical education in the pattern of general education it is important to present the belief role of physical education in post. In the past it reflected the

philosophy of people and frequently revealed the dominant purpose of the body of the state. Some people of the past who believed in subjecting the body as a mean of elevating the soul of disagreed enjoyable physical activity. Today's education is not merely a vast sea of mental acrobatics but also a source of physical activity that leads to all round perfection of an individual. Most psychologists agree that attitude arise from human needs. Sometimes these may determine only the content of attitude but not their object. At other time needs may determine both the content and object of attitudes. Current psychologist regards the existence of strong feelings about something as psychologically more important then what the feeling are about. Hostility can produce aggressive attitudes in an individual; it is an accident of time and place that such feeling are as anti –Semitism and anti – Catholicism exists. No doubt such strong emphasis on the psychological cause of attitude ignores certain important social and political determines of attitudes, however it is psychological case that convent the predisposition into an action on statement of belief or opinion. Attitude changes as the result of experience. Very some of us had fixed an immutable attitude of whole life such as the women conditions and a give internal hope to those who wish to reform society and rid it of its conflicts and pathologies. An attitude in mental and neural state of readiness organized or through experience exerting a directive dynamic influence upon the individual response to all objects and situations with which it is related. Attitude is revealed by the way act towards the population groups and society. They are not action themselves; they are the conditions within ourselves which cause as to act in certain ways. They are predisposition to action and expression of belief and opinion. Attitude is general disposition which stands behind our emotional feelings. Attitude do not always cause is to act in consistent ways indeed people's behavior is often so in consistent that we can only suppose that it represent attitude that are inconsistent and logically contradictory or to put it another way predisposition's vary from time to time, sometimes however only appears to be inconsistent because social pressure, politeness or timidity may dispose us to hid our true sentiment. Attitude drive basically from value systems and beliefs related to one self, work and relationship with peoples. The way of acquiring knowledge and skill are in part of a function of our attitude. Attitude will also determine the application of knowledge and skill are technique in addition,

attitude are important are in determining coaching, competencies success. They tell us what kind of need is dominated in a certain period of time.

Methodology

The subjects selected for this study were 60 students from different medical college of Indore; they served as subjects and were selected randomly. Criterion measure for testing the hypothesis in this study was the score obtained from self prepared questionnaire filled by the student's different medical college from Indore. The questionnaire used for this study was a self prepared questionnaire, which was constructed by the research scholar himself. Statements arranged in questionnaire were related to attitude and simple statement. Each of the statement described for knowing the attitude of medical students towards games and sports. All the subjects were given their responses to questionnaire prepared by the scholar. Attitude towards physical education questionnaire consist two point scales such as "YES" and "NO".

Chi-square (χ^2) Tabulated standard value obtained 3, 841, at 0.05 level of significance.

Q.NO.	Positive response	Negative response	X2 cal	Ho. Acc/Rej
1	52	8	32.26	Ho. Reject
2	55	5	41.6	Ho. Reject
3	56	4	45.06	Ho. Reject
4	46	14	17.06	Ho. Reject
5	48	12	21.6	Ho. Reject
6	52	8	32.26	Ho. Reject
7	51	9	29.4	Ho. Reject
8	52	8	32.26	Ho. Reject
9	26	34	1.06	Ho. Reject
10	41	19	8.06	Ho. Reject
11	50	10	26.66	Ho. Reject

12	44	16	13.06	Ho. Reject
13	52	8	32.26	Ho. Reject
14	41	19	8.06	Ho. Reject
15	51	9	29.4	Ho. Reject
16	34	26	1.06	Ho. Reject
17	46	14	17.06	Ho. Reject
18	49	11	24.06	Ho. Reject
19	40	20	6.66	Ho. Reject
20	39	21	5.4	Ho. Reject

The findings of the study revealed that in most of the questions the attitude of medical students is positive towards games and sports but in some questions their thinking and mentality vary from the system. According to the analysis of data it is revealed that the students liked to participate in activity of games and sports wanted to develop interest of students towards the games and sports.

Conclusions

To know the attitude of medical college students towards games and sports of the 20 questions were selected for questionnaire in which response, 34 questions were found positive attitude of principals towards games and sports.

Some positive responses are as follows:-

- Principals were whole heartedly and happy towards games and sports activities of their institutions.
- They thought that a student becomes more disciplined by games and sports.
- They thought that their institution provides better ground management, equipment and other sports facility to the students.
- They thought that there should be compulsory education of games and sports in every institution and school of present day.

- They thought that a student become more self confident because of games and sports.
- They thought that a student get well mentally developed because of games and sports.
- They thought that a student have friendly nature towards all because of games and sports.
- They thought that games and sports bring feeling of team unity to be developed among the students.
- Principal were interested to encourage girl to participate in games and sports.
- Principal provide help to physical education teacher in games and sports.
- They thought that games and sports are essential for overall development of students.
- They thought that with help of games and sports treatment of mentally weak students can be possible.

Some response showed negative attitudes were:-

- Principal have difference in opinion with physical education teacher of their institution.
- They thought that No special importance is given to games and sports in private institution.
- They thought that students pay more attention to their studies as compare to games and sports.
- They thought that use bad language and abusive words in game and sports.

Therefore the response of 89% questions found of positive response, 2% questions found negative and 9% questions of found natural.

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